

The study on the ballistic performance and failure mechanism of UHMWPE-Aramid1414 fiber hybrid composites

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Abstract: The armor plates of hybrid composites with 0°/90° unidirectional (UD) structure used in this paper were produced by hot press, which reinforcement was the hybrid of Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE) fiber and Aramid1414 fiber, and which resin matrix was Waterborne Polyurethane (WPU) or Epoxy resin (EP). The ballistic performance of hybrid composites was studied through a series of V50 ballistic tests with steel-core bullet. The fractured morphologies of the armor plates were observed by the stereomicroscopy. Finally, the damage mechanism of hybrid composites was analyzed. It is shown from the results that the ballistic performance of UHMWPE-Aramid1414 fiber hybrid composites was superior to that of the single fiber reinforced composites. For the hybrid composites, the better ballistic performance was achieved when UHMWPE fiber composites worked as strike face and Aramid1414 fiber composites as rear face. The fractured morphologies of the hybrid composites were fiber shear plugging on the strike face, shear failure after tensile deformation of the fiber in the interior of the armor plate, fiber tensile fracture on rear face, fiber pull-out and lamination of the armor plate. Tensile deformation and tensile fracture of the fiber is the primary way of energy absorption when the armor plate was impacted by the steel-core bullets.

Brief introduction:

Table 1: The parameters and V50 values of hybrid composites armor plates

NO	Resin	UD sheet		Thickness /mm	Fiber volume fraction/%	The type fiber of strike surface	V50*
		hybrid weight ratio/%	Areal density / (kg m ⁻²)				
		Aramid1414 /					
		UHMWPE					
#1		0/100	9.92	10.00	90.49	—	100.00
#2		100/0	10.04	7.23	88.24		90.91
#3		30/70	9.89	9.62	93.76		117.13
#4	WPU	50/50	9.93	9.02	85.23	Aramid1414	104.90
#5		65/35	9.94	8.87	82.05		110.84
#6		40/60	10.01	9.29	86.40		132.87
#7		50/50	10.11	9.19	85.23	UHMWPE	148.60
#8		80/20	9.96	8.44	81.53		105.24
#9	EP	50/50	10.68	9.56	89.75	UHMWPE	110.66
#10		50/50	10.65	9.54	89.75	Aramid1414	101.40

Note: The V50* is normalized by the corresponding value of #1 composites armor plate.

Fig 1: Influences of strike face on the ballistic performance of hybrid composites armor plates

The ballistic limit velocity of 50/50 hybrid composites armor plate with similar fiber volume fractions, areal density and thickness in WPU resin system or EP resin system were shown as Fig.1. It could be seen from Fig.1 that the higher ballistic limit velocity were obtained when the UHMWPE fiber composites were put on the strike face and Aramid1414 fiber composites were put on the rear face of the hybrid composites respectively whether in WPU resin system or in EP resin system.

When the aramid1414 fiber composites worked as the strike face materials and the UHMWPE fiber composites worked as the rear face materials. The two component materials of hybrid composites were destroyed one by one resulting from the poor synergistic effect between aramid1414 fiber composites and UHMWPE fiber composites. In contrary, the two component materials of hybrid composites were destroyed simultaneously. The synergistic effect between aramid1414 fiber composites and UHMWPE fiber composites was perfect.

The fracture morphology of hybrid composites armor plates was consistent with the previous theoretical analysis.

Fig 2: Aramid1414 fiber/UHMWPE fiber (50/50) reinforced WPU resin matrix hybrid composites armor plates
(a: the left is strike face, the right is rear face; b: the connect interface of hybrid composites armor plates; c & d: the connect interface around bullet holes)

Fig 3: UHMWPE fiber/ Aramid1414 fiber (50/50) reinforced WPU resin matrix hybrid composites armor plates
(a: the left is strike face, the right is rear face; b: the connect interface of hybrid composites armor plates; c & d: the connect interface around bullet holes)

Fig 4: The surface in the bullet hole of UHMWPE fiber/ Aramid1414 fiber (50/50) reinforced WPU resin matrix composites armor plates
 (a: The surface in the bullet hole of UHMWPE fiber composites; b: The surface in the bullet hole of Aramid1414 fiber composites; c: Fiber tensile deformation; d: Fiber shear failure)

Fig 5: The schematic diagram of the penetration of steel-core bullet into the hybrid composites armor plates
 (a: shock wave; b: shear plug & fiber tensile deformation & fiber tensile fracture & delamination; c: shear fracture & delamination & bulging; d: shear fracture & delamination & bulging)

The surface of Aramid1414 fiber/UHMWPE fiber (50/50) and UHMWPE fiber/Aramid 1414 fiber (50/50) reinforced WPU resin composites armor plates after ballistic tests were shown as Fig.2 and Fig.3, respectively. The inner surface morphologies of the bullet hole in UHMWPE fiber/Aramid1414 fiber (50/50) reinforced WPU resin matrix composites armor plates were shown as Fig.4. To sum up, the schematic diagram of the steel-core bullet into the UHMWPE-Aramid1414 fiber hybrid composites armor plates were shown as Fig.5. The composites armor plate occurred shear plugging, fiber tensile deformation and being shear, delamination of armor plates, fibers tensioned to failure in the rear face and bulge along with

the bullet penetration path.

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